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Toxic metals in rivers: Analysis of fish scales as indicators of pollution

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1 TABLE OF CONTENTS

2	Aims of the thesis	3
3	Introduction	4
3.1	General Characteristics of Ray-Finned Fish	4
3.2	Fish Scale	5
3.3	Chub (<i>Leuciscus cephalus</i>)	6
3.4	Heavy Metals and Their Toxicity	7
3.4.1	Mercury	7
3.4.2	Lead	7
3.4.3	Cadmium	7
3.4.4	Copper	8
3.5	Bioaccumulation of Heavy Metals in Freshwater Ecosystems	8
3.6	Fish Scale as a Sampling Material	9
4	Experimental part	10
4.1	Sampling	10
4.2	Sample Preparation and Cleaning	11
5	Results and Discussion	12
5.1	Use of Fish Scales for Monitoring Contaminants	12
5.2	Age of Fish Correlating with Their Length	13
5.3	Copper Analysis	14
5.4	Cadmium Analysis	15
5.5	Lead Analysis	16
6	Conclusion	17
7	List of Figures, Tables, and Graphs	18
8	References	19

Annotation

This study focuses on the use of fish scales as indicators of toxic metal pollution in river ecosystems. Toxic metals such as lead, cadmium, and mercury are often present in river waters due to human activities and industrial pollution. Analyzing fish scales could provide a useful tool for monitoring pollution levels in waterways and assessing ecological risks to aquatic life.

Keywords

Heavy metals, pollution of watercourses, fish scales, wastewater treatment plant, mine water treatment plant, ICP-MS, river ecosystem, Jihlava river, Oslava river

List of Abbreviations

WWTP – Wastewater treatment plant

MWTP – Mine water treatment plant

SCI MUNI – Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno

UCT Prague – University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague

ICP-OES – Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry

ICP-MS – Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry

MQ water – ultrapure water

PE – Polyethylene

LDPE – Low-Density Polyethylene

MRS – Moravian Fishing Union

Abv. – above

Und. – under

2 AIMS OF THE THESIS

The aim of my work is to analyze the level of contamination in the Oslava and Jihlava rivers by heavy metals before and after the discharge points of wastewater treatment plants and mine water treatment plants, using environmentally friendly collected sampling material (fish scales). Another objective is to demonstrate the relationship between the measured metal concentrations and the age, length of the fish, and changes in concentration levels along the river's flow. All scales come from a single fish species (Chub, *Leuciscus cephalus*). The fish were caught near the wastewater and mine water treatment plant sites in Oslavany, Náměšť nad Oslavou, and Ivančice. Selected heavy metals (lead, mercury, copper, cadmium, arsenic) were analyzed using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS).

3 INTRODUCTION

The development of the electrical and mining industries leads to an increasing amount of heavy and toxic metals in the hydrosphere. These substances negatively affect not only aquatic organisms but can also pose health risks to humans through the consumption of contaminated fish. Traditionally, fish contamination monitoring is done by analyzing muscle tissue or internal organs, but fish scale analysis can offer a more environmentally friendly alternative. This method does not require killing the fish and allows for easy, long-term sample storage, which can be useful for future analyses and comparisons.

The aim of this thesis was to assess whether wastewater or mine water treatment plants contribute to the contamination of rivers through the analysis of fish scales. Increased contamination of the river with heavy metals could result from insufficient treatment of wastewater, mine water, or sewage sludge. Sampling was conducted near the Ivančice and Náměšť nad Oslavou wastewater treatment plants and the Oslavany mine water treatment plant. These sites were chosen because, unlike other treatment plants on the Jihlava and Oslava rivers, they discharge relatively large amounts of treated water back into the river, making the impact on the water flow more detectable (measurable).

The results of this work could contribute to the development of sustainable methods for monitoring heavy metal contamination in aquatic ecosystems.

3.1 General Characteristics of Ray-Finned Fish

The term "fish" is somewhat problematic because, in the past, it also referred to jawless vertebrates – lampreys (Cyclostomata), as well as cartilaginous fish (Chondrichthyes), ray-finned fish (Actinopterygii), and lobe-finned fish (Sarcopterygii) (Dvořák et al., 2020) (Šíma, 2023) (Janáková, 2013). It is the largest class of vertebrates, comprising between 24,000 and 35,000 species, depending on the source (Musilová, 2016).

3.2 Fish Scale

The fish scale is one of the few skin derivatives of ray-finned fish. Its main function is considered to be protection against external threats, such as infection or injury caused by abrasion. A thin layer of mucus on the surface of the scale, produced by the skin, reduces friction on the fish's body surface and facilitates movement in the aquatic environment. When a scale is lost, the fish is exposed to the risk of infection in the exposed area, and the skin becomes more vulnerable at that point (Nováková, 2009; Dvořák et al., 2020). Ray-finned fish develop scales shortly after hatching, and their number increases with age. Scales grow throughout the fish's life, and their growth is directly dependent on factors such as water oxygen concentration, water temperature (seasonal changes), physical and mental condition, availability of food, and many other aspects (Nováková, 2009; Dvořák et al., 2020). The basic structure of a ray-finned fish scale is the so-called scale plate, made of immature bone cells. The scale plate grows from one side into the dermis, where the scale remains anchored throughout its life. On the opposite side, away from the body, another part of the scale grows, which is visible on the surface of the fish's body. This part is covered by skin, which produces mucus.

Fish scales develop and grow gradually due to material (lamellar bone) produced by specialized cells located in the dermis, called scleroblasts. The dermis is a layer of skin made of collagen fibers, and its purpose is to connect the skin to the muscles. The dermis is likely an important link between the overall heavy metal load on the fish's body and the sampled scale. Since the dermis is a well-vascularized area, heavy metal compounds may easily be transported from the blood into the scale's structure. Therefore, fish scale sampling can indicate not only direct contamination from the external environment but also the overall load on the fish organism (Dvořák et al., 2020; Mendel University, 2000). The scale (scale plate) is continuously expanded by so-called lamellae (sclerites), which are limited growth rings of the scale. To visualize this, we can think of lamellae as tree rings. Thanks to the lamellae, we can easily determine the age of the fish, as the scale growth during winter is dark in color, while the summer growth is light or white in color (Figure 2) (Nováková, 2009; Dvořák et al., 2020). Cycloid scales are present in carp-like fish, including the chub, and therefore all the scales we collected are of the cycloid type (Dvořák et al., 2020).

Figure 1 Internal organ arrangement of fish; modified; adapted from K. M. Ismail, 2024

Figure 2 Cycloid scale of the chub; adapted from M. Horáček, 2010

3.3 Chub (*Leuciscus cephalus*)

The chub (*Leuciscus cephalus*) is a very typical fish for nearly all flowing waters in the Czech Republic. Its characteristic feature is its body shape, which is typically elongated and cylindrical. It is found in fast-flowing sections of rivers or reservoirs. While the chub can occasionally grow larger than 60 cm, individuals typically range from 20 to 40 cm in size. Identifying the chub from other river fish is not difficult, as it has a reddish orange colored anal fin. The chub is omnivorous and actively forages for food throughout the year. Only during periods of severe cold does its desire for food decrease (M. Horáček, 2017; M. Horáček, 2010).

Figure 3 European chub; adapted from Š. Jonáková, 2012

Figure 4 Europeane chub caught in Oslavany

3.4 Heavy Metals and Their Toxicity

Heavy metals are a natural component of the Earth's crust and are released into aquatic environments through erosion, volcanic activity, or human activities. Heavy metals are released into the environment, for example, through the combustion of fossil fuels, mining, and pesticide use. Not all heavy metals are toxic; some are essential in certain amounts for humans and selected animals (e.g., zinc, copper, iron). In contrast, toxic heavy metals include lead, mercury, arsenic, and cadmium. These metals often cause enzyme blockages, damage to biomembranes, or even cancer. They are teratogenic, reduce fertility, cause poisoning, and in some cases, anemia (Velíšek et al., 2014; Bartošová, 2017; Dobrotová, 2011).

3.4.1 Mercury

Mercury (Hg) is a silvery heavy metal that naturally occurs and is liquid at normal temperature and pressure. It exists in nature in several forms, such as elemental Hg^0 , as well as Hg^{1+} and Hg^{2+} . Some of the most common mercury compounds include methylmercury, dimethylmercury, HgS , $\text{Hg}(\text{OH})_2$, and HgCl_2 . In aquatic environments, mercury primarily occurs in the form of complexes with inorganic or organic ligands, as well as in the form of hydroxides or chlorides (the compounds mentioned above) (Velíšek et al., 2014; Bobrowska-Grzesik et al., 2013).

3.4.2 Lead

It is shiny, ductile, and has a low melting point. It is also known as a superconductor. Lead can exist in three oxidation states: Pb^0 , Pb^{2+} , and Pb^{4+} , with its raw form, Pb^0 , being found in nature only very rarely. In aquatic environments, lead is found in the form of the following compounds: $[\text{PbCO}_3(\text{aq})]^0$, $[\text{PbOH}]^{1+}$, $[\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2(\text{aq})]^0$. Upon entering the body of an organism, lead binds to red blood cells and, within several dozen minutes, is deposited in the bones and soft tissues (Velíšek et al., 2014; Bobrowska-Grzesik et al., 2013).

3.4.3 Cadmium

It is highly resistant to rust, which is why it is used as a coating layer on other metals. Its release into aquatic environments is primarily caused by erosion, and cadmium appears here in the

form of the hydrocomplex $\text{Cd}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$. This metal is toxic and undergoes bioaccumulation within the food chain (Velíšek et al., 2014; Bobrowska-Grzesik et al., 2013; A. Šípek, 2011).

3.4.4 Copper

Copper (Cu) is a reddish noble metal that occurs rarely in its pure form in nature but primarily exists in more than 600 copper ores. Examples include chalcopyrite (CuFeS_2) and azurite ($2\text{CuCO}_3 \cdot \text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$). Copper, as an element, can be found in compounds in oxidation states I, II, and III, with compounds where copper has an oxidation state of II being the most common and widely spread. These include, for example, CuO , CuS , CuCO_3 , $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$. (M. Daňková, 2016; Champika SSK Gamakaranage et al., 2011; Bobrowska-Grzesik et al., 2013; Wikiskripta, 2022).

3.5 Bioaccumulation of Heavy Metals in Freshwater Ecosystems

Pollution is generally divided into natural pollution (e.g., geochemical, biological) and anthropogenic pollution (caused by human activity). Heavy metals can be released into water through the so-called geochemical cycle, which ensures the continuous circulation of substances in the rock environment. In terms of the fate of heavy metals, we are concerned with both dissolved and undissolved metal compounds in water. Insoluble heavy metals in water may form their own minerals or be adsorbed onto the surface of other minerals; these processes also occur during natural processes in aquatic ecosystems (e.g., rock erosion). It is also crucial to consider the concentration of heavy metal compounds in sediments, as well as the concentration of dissolved oxygen in the water, acid-neutralizing capacity, presence of complexing compounds, concentrations of organic substances, calcium, and sodium. These compounds (whether toxic or non-toxic) enter fish bodies through several pathways (food, gills, skin). Foreign substances typically enter the fish body through the gill epithelium, as the skin is a much more resistant diffusion barrier. The only exception is the early developmental stages of fish, which still have thin skin and very small gill surface areas (Velíšek et al., 2014).

Once heavy metal compounds (both toxic and non-toxic) enter the digestive tract, some of these substances are excreted with the feces, while the non-excreted portion passes through the intestinal biomembrane into the bloodstream. How these toxic and non-toxic substances move from the intestines into the bloodstream is not yet entirely clear. The blood then transports metal

compounds throughout the fish's body to various organs, where heavy metals are stored in a manner similar to humans (in the liver, in proteins, or in the blood – erythrocytes) (Velíšek et al., 2014; Wikiskripta, 2023). Some toxic metal compounds have the ability to bioaccumulate within the food chain. Bioaccumulation is the process by which toxic substances accumulate in organisms at higher trophic levels. The most affected fish and generally organisms are always apex predators (those at the top of the food pyramid). In fish, this includes predatory species such as the northern pike, European perch, or common zander, among others.

Figure 5 Biogeochemical cycle of heavy metals; created using BioRender

Figure 6 Principle of bioaccumulation; created using BioRender

3.6 Fish Scale as a Sampling Material

The use of fish scales as a gently obtained sampling material has already been addressed in several studies, with similar overall objectives. The main aim was to highlight sampling methods that do not require the fish to be killed or stunned — a significant difference compared to sampling liver or muscle tissue. However, the primary focus of these studies was to determine whether the scale can adequately reflect the overall burden of heavy metals in the fish organism and thus provide reliable data, as has been demonstrated with sampled fins, liver, or muscle tissue (Katarina Jovičić et al., 2023; A. Cobelo-García et al., 2017). Another study aimed to demonstrate a correlation between the concentration of heavy metals in fish scales and their deformation (Tayyaba Sultana et al., 2017).

4 EXPERIMENTAL PART

4.1 Sampling

The sampling of fish and subsequent collection of their scales took place from February 4, 2024, to September 10, 2024. Each sample consisted of one to ten scales, which were removed at the level of the lateral line and approximately in the middle of the fish's body. A total of 40 samples were collected, specifically: 36 samples of *Leuciscus cephalus* scales, 1 sample of *Cyprinus carpio* scales, 1 sample of *Abramis brama* scales, 1 sample of *Rutilus rutilus* scales, and 1 sample of *Leuciscus cephalus* scales. The scales of fish other than *Leuciscus cephalus* will serve for interspecies comparison. All of these fish were caught by rod and the scales were collected immediately after the fish were brought ashore. The fish were caught at three locations: the Oslava River in Oslavany and Náměšť nad Oslavou, and the Jihlava River in Ivančice. The specific river sections were selected based on potential pollution sources. These included wastewater treatment plants (WWTP in Náměšť nad Oslavou and Ivančice) and a mine water treatment plant (MWTP in Oslavany). The sampling was first conducted upstream of the pollution source and then downstream, ensuring that at least two water obstacles (weirs) separated the two sampling points.

Sampling site:	Description of sampling sites:	Number of caught fish:
Náměšť nad Oslavou	Above WWTP (49.2047242N, 16.1583003E)	6
	Under WWTP (49.1961853N, 16.1602853E)	8
Oslavany	Above MWTP (49.1265583N, 16.3294789E)	11
	Under MWTP (49.0975019N, 16.3661864E)	6
Ivančice	Above WWTP (49.0974739N, 16.3670808E)	6
	Under WWTP (49.0922617N, 16.4004689E)	3

Table 1 List of sampling sites

Figure 7 Scheme of the sampling site Ivančice; map data adapted from Mapy.cz

All fish were caught using a rod, either by spinning or float fishing. Once landed, the fish was taken out of the water with a wetted landing net and placed on damp grass or a pre-prepared mat. It was then measured using a wooden measuring board, and between one and ten scales were removed with tweezers. The scales were placed between two sheets of paper, and the location and date of capture, species, and size of the fish were recorded on the paper. The paper with the scales was then stored in a resealable polyethylene bag and kept at room temperature in a dry environment until the time of cleaning (in some cases exceeding six months). A visual inspection of the wound from the scale removal was then performed, and the fish was gently returned to the water.

I attempted to estimate the age of individual fish based on the number of scale annuli myself. Using a hand-held magnifying glass with 10× magnification and a dark background, I counted the winter annuli and used them to approximate the age of the fish.

4.2 Sample Preparation and Cleaning

All samples were removed from their polyethylene bags and paper double-layers and subsequently transferred into pre-prepared, deionized water-rinsed, and numbered glass test tubes. Deionized water was added to each tube until approximately $\frac{3}{4}$ full. The tubes then underwent three 10-minute ultrasonic cleaning cycles. Using a glass rod and Teflon tweezers, the individual samples were transferred into numbered Eppendorf microtubes. The samples were then dried in a laboratory fume hood at ambient room temperature. Sample digestion for ICP-MS analysis was carried out as

follows: approximately 6 to 20 mg of each sample was weighed using analytical balances, and the measured portions were placed into pre-labelled polyethylene tubes and sealed. Three additional subsamples from the leftover material of samples 19, 26, and 32 were also weighed and labelled as 19SP, 26SP, and 32SP. These served as reference samples. Five additional polyethylene tubes were left empty and used as blank controls.

To prepare the samples for ICP-MS analysis, it was necessary to dissolve the fish scales to obtain a suitable solution. Each tube received 1 mL of 68% nitric acid and 100 μ L of a gold solution (10 mg/L Au) to prevent mercury losses during digestion and storage. To aid the digestion process, tubes were placed in a thermostat and heated for 90 minutes at 75.5 °C. Fifteen minutes before the end of this cycle, three drops of hydrogen peroxide were added to accelerate oxidation. After the 90-minute digestion, all scales were fully dissolved. The sample volumes were then adjusted to 9.7 mL with deionized water. This constituted the final form of the samples prepared for ICP-MS analysis. The concentrations of Cu, As, Cd, Pb, and Hg were analyzed using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (Agilent 7700x ICP-MS). The measurements were performed in helium collision mode to reduce polyatomic interferences from the sample matrix. Internal standards (^{45}Sc , ^{72}Ge , ^{115}In , ^{209}Bi) were used to correct for matrix effects and signal drift. The method's performance was validated using identical fish scale samples spiked with known concentrations of each metal, with recovery rates ranging between 90% and 110%.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Use of Fish Scales for Monitoring Contaminants

In recent years, the trend of using fish scales as a matrix for measuring concentrations of various foreign substances has been growing strongly. Fish scales offer several advantages. One of them is their constant contact with the environment, particularly with water and, to some extent, with the sediment on the bottom. The scale should also reflect the overall heavy metal burden of the organism, as its nourishment occurs through a well-vascularized dermis. Through the dermis, substances from the blood can be transported or stored in the scales. Another major advantage of sampling fish scales is their easy storage, which is not time-limited, as long as the scale is properly dried. The ease of collection is also crucial, requiring only tweezers and disinfection to clean the

wound. The biggest advantage of using scales as a sampling material is the minimal injury to the fish. Earlier studies measuring heavy metals most often used liver, muscle, or fin preparations to measure concentrations of unwanted substances. As a result, the fish had to be killed. This, however, eliminates the possibility of ongoing measurement of the substance concentration in a single individual over time, and further, capturing a larger number of fish may endanger the population of the species being caught. We chose chub (*Leuciscus cephalus*) for our research because it is an omnivorous fish, which can be interesting from the perspective of heavy metal accumulation in their bodies. It takes in metals from both plant-based and animal-based food, such as small fish and crustaceans. The second reason for choosing chub is its widespread occurrence in nearly all watercourses in the Czech Republic. Since all the fish from which we took samples were caught with a fishing rod, this significantly increased our chances of a catch.

5.2 Age of Fish Correlating with Their Length

I determined the age of the fish myself, without previous extensive experience. For individuals smaller than 18 cm, it was very difficult to count the winter growth rings. In some cases, I was unable to determine the winter growth rings. For the other fish, where I managed to determine the age by counting the winter annuli of the scales, the age may be affected by false rings. These can occur when the fish experiences prolonged starvation or is exposed to long-term stress. In graph number 1, we can see how length correlates with the age of the fish. In all locations, a very similar growth rate is observed, although the length of the fish in relation to their age appears optically smaller in the Oslavany above the mine water treatment plant (MWTP) location. Fish at this location grow a bit slower compared to the other locations. The slower growth could be due to colder water or a lack of water productivity.

The age of the fish was determined in order to assess how the age of the fish influences the accumulation of heavy metals in their scales and whether we can compare fish of different ages. Based on the measurements, it was found that the length of the fish is closely correlated with their age (figure 8), and we will continue to consider only the length of the fish, as it is more accurately measurable.

Figure 8 Age of fish correlated with length

5.3 Copper Analysis

The copper concentrations analyzed in the scales of *Leuciscus cephalus* ranged from 0.32 $\mu\text{g/g}$ to 5.38 $\mu\text{g/g}$. At the Oslavany site, both under and above the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP), it cannot be conclusively said that copper concentrations decrease with the increasing length (or age) of the fish. At the Náměšť nad Oslavou site, both under and above the WWTP, a slight trend of decreasing concentration with age and fish length is observed. However, this trend does not appear consistently in all fish caught at this location, and therefore it cannot be stated that copper concentrations in scales decrease with increasing fish length. The trend of increasing/decreasing concentration with length was not confirmed, which allows for comparisons of concentrations independently of the age and length of the fish. When comparing the median copper concentrations at sites under and above potential sources of contamination, the median value at the site under the potential contamination source is higher in both cases. The difference is on the order of one to two tenths of a microgram, thus not statistically significant. Ultimately, the median values suggest that the copper contamination in the Oslava River increases downstream. The median value at the Náměšť nad Oslavou site above the WWTP was 0.51 $\mu\text{g/g}$, and under the WWTP, it was 0.71 $\mu\text{g/g}$. At the Oslavany site (further downstream), the median value above the mine water treatment plant (MWTP) was 0.89 $\mu\text{g/g}$, and under the MWTP, it was 0.99 $\mu\text{g/g}$. This

would indicate that there is no gradual dilution of copper contamination, but rather an increase in contamination downstream. However, since the median difference is at most four-tenths of a microgram, this increase in contamination cannot be considered significant. The slight contamination may be caused by insufficiently treated mining or wastewater, improper handling at fish farms in Oslavany (copper – a component of some feed mixtures), or road and rail transport.

5.4 Cadmium Analysis

The cadmium concentrations measured in the fish scales of *Leuciscus cephalus* ranged from 0.0020 µg/g to 0.0398 µg/g. At the Oslavany sites (above and under MWTP), the concentration does not increase with the fish's length. In the case of the Náměšť' site, the concentration of cadmium slightly increases with the fish's length. However, this increase is on the borderline of significance, allowing for comparisons of concentrations even among fish of different sizes.

At the Oslavany site (both above and under MWTP), the difference in medians is 0.0122 µg/g, which may indicate that the Oslava River is slightly contaminated with cadmium downstream of MWTP. The Oslava River in the Náměšť' section above and under the wastewater treatment plant shows exactly the opposite trend compared to the Oslavany section. Based on the difference in medians, it seems that cadmium contamination is being diluted. However, the decrease in the median cadmium concentration in the fish scales of *Leuciscus cephalus* is not significant. The cadmium analysis reveals a different trend compared to copper contamination. The median values for the Náměšť' site were 0.0159 µg/g above the wastewater treatment plant and 0.0096 µg/g under it. At the Oslavany site, the median values were 0.0046 µg/g above MWTP and 0.0168 µg/g under MWTP. At the Náměšť' section, there could be a slight dilution of cadmium concentration, but the median difference is only six thousandths of a microgram, so it cannot be considered significant. At the Oslavany section above MWTP (compared to Náměšť' downstream), there was a decrease in concentration (to 0.0046 µg/g). This median concentration is borderline significantly lower than at other sampling sites. Subsequently, there was a sharp increase in concentration at the Oslavany site under MWTP (increase to 0.0168 µg/g). This increase can be considered borderline significant, meaning that the river may be more heavily contaminated with cadmium in the section flowing through Oslavany, where wastewater from mine water treatment

facilities discharges. The cadmium burden in the river could be caused by inadequately treated mine water, road and rail traffic, or runoff from agricultural fields.

5.5 Lead Analysis

The lead concentrations measured in the fish scales of *Leuciscus cephalus* ranged from 0.125 µg/g to 1.210 µg/g. The lead concentrations in the scales of fish caught in the Oslava River section above and under MWTP decrease with increasing length and age of the fish, but this decrease is on the borderline of significance. In the case of the Náměšť site, no trend of increasing or decreasing concentration with the growth of the fish is observed. The increase/decrease in heavy metal concentrations with the length (age) of the fish is on the threshold of significance, which allows for the comparison of heavy metal concentrations in the scales independently of the fish's length (age). The median difference at the Oslavany site above and under MWTP is 0.425 µg/g. This difference can be considered borderline significant, meaning that the river is slightly contaminated with lead in the direction of flow. The median difference at the Náměšť site above and under the wastewater treatment plant is 0.112 µg/g. This difference is only in the range of one-tenth of a microgram and is not significant.

From the given median values of lead concentrations, it follows that in three out of four cases across the sampling sites, the difference was only 0.1 µg/g. A larger increase was recorded only at the Oslavany site under MWTP. The median concentration at the Náměšť site above the wastewater treatment plant was 0.319 µg/g and under it 0.431 µg/g. This increase cannot be considered significant. The median at the Oslavany site above MWTP was 0.305 µg/g and under MWTP 0.730 µg/g. The decrease in lead concentration between the Náměšť site under the wastewater treatment plant and the Oslavany site above MWTP could be influenced by the number of small tributaries feeding into the Oslava River. At the Oslavany site under MWTP, an increase in the median lead concentrations in the fish scales is observed. The measured values at this site are insignificantly higher than at the other sites. The potential contamination of the Oslava River in the section flowing through Oslavany could be influenced by inadequately treated mine water, the proximity of the former coal spoil heap, or road and rail traffic.

6 CONCLUSION

The thesis focuses on the use of chub (*Leuciscus cephalus*) fish scales as an effective and environmentally friendly sampling material that can reflect the contamination of watercourses with heavy metals. The aim of the study was to analyze the contamination levels of the Oslava and Jihlava Rivers with heavy metals using the gently collected sampling material.

Based on the median data of copper concentrations, it can be concluded that the river's pollution increases downstream. The copper concentrations were as follows: 0.51 µg/g (Náměšť, above the WWTP); 0.71 µg/g (Náměšť, under the WWTP); 0.89 µg/g (Oslavany, above MWTP); and 0.99 µg/g (Oslavany, under MWTP). No clear correlation between increasing copper concentration and increasing fish length was observed. However, at the Náměšť site, a slight trend of decreasing concentration with increasing fish length was evident.

According to the median concentrations of cadmium in the scales of the chub, contamination of the river with cadmium decreases downstream at the Náměšť site. This suggests that the section of the river, where the Náměšť wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) discharges, is not contaminated with cadmium. In contrast, at the Oslavany site, a borderline significant increase in concentration was observed, indicating cadmium contamination in that section of the river. At Náměšť, the concentration of cadmium slightly increases with fish length, but this change is not significant.

The comparison of lead concentrations in chub scales showed an increase in concentration at both river sections. At Náměšť, the concentration increased from 0.319 µg/g (above the WWTP) to 0.431 µg/g (under the WWTP). At Oslavany, the concentration increased from 0.305 µg/g (above MWTP) to 0.730 µg/g (under MWTP). These values indicate that the river is slightly contaminated with lead at both the WWTP and MWTP sections, with a dilution of this contamination downstream, as evidenced by the median concentrations at Náměšť under the WWTP and Oslavany above MWTP (slight decrease downstream). A decrease in concentration with increasing fish length is observed at the Oslavany site. At Náměšť, no relationship between fish growth and lead concentration in the scales was noted.

Sampling site:	Median of concentrations Cd (µg/g):	Median of concentrations Cu (µg/g):	Median of concentrations Pb (µg/g):
Náměšť n. O. abv. WWTP	0.0159	0.51	0.319
Náměšť n. O. und. WWTP	0.0096	0.71	0.431
Oslavany abv. MWTP	0.0046	0.89	0.305
Oslavany und. MWTP	0.0168	0.99	0.730

Table 2 Median concentrations detected

The mercury and arsenic analysis of chub scales did not provide suitable data for statistical evaluation, likely due to insufficient sample weight caused by the small number of scales collected from the selected individuals. To successfully analyse heavy metals, at least ten scales must be collected (more for smaller fish), ensuring a minimum sample weight of 20 mg.

Heavy metals have always been and remain a threat not only to aquatic ecosystems but also to human health. This issue is more relevant today than ever before, and the chub fish scale has proven to be an effective and, most importantly, environmentally friendly sampling material that can reflect the contamination of watercourses with heavy metals.

7 LIST OF FIGURES, TABLES, AND GRAPHS

<i>Figure 1</i> Internal organ arrangement of fish; modified; adapted from K. M. Ismail, 2024.....	6
<i>Figure 2</i> Cycloid scale of the chub; adapted from M. Horáček, 2010.....	6
<i>Figure 3</i> European chup; adapted from Š. Jonáková, 2012.....	6
<i>Figure 4</i> Europeane chub caught in Oslavany.....	6
<i>Figure 5</i> Biogeochemical cycle of heavy metals; created using BioRender.....	9
<i>Figure 6</i> Principle of bioaccumulation; created using BioRender.....	9
<i>Figure 7</i> Scheme of the sampling site Ivančice; map data adapted from Mapy.cz.....	11
<i>Figure 8</i> Age of fish correlated with length.....	14
<i>Table 1</i> List of sampling sites	10
<i>Table 2</i> Median concentrations detected	18

8 REFERENCES

- BARTOŠOVÁ, Martina. *Těžké kovy v povrchových vodách*. Online, Seminární práce. Brno: Masarykova univerzita, Přírodovědecká fakulta, 2017. Dostupné z: https://is.muni.cz/el/sci/podzim2017/Bi7520/um/seminarni_prace/Tezke_kovy_v_povrchovy_vodach.pdf. [cit. 2025-02-09].
- BIORENDER. BioRender. Online. ©2025. Dostupné z: <https://www.biorender.com/> [cit. 2025-02-10].
- BOBROWSKA-GRZESIK, Ewa. *Chemical elements: compendium*. Český Těšín: 2 Theta, 2013. ISBN 978-80-86380-66-7.
- COBELO-GARCÍA, Antonio; MORÁN, Paloma; ALMÉCJA, Clara a CABALLERO, Pablo. Historical record of trace elements (1983–2007) in scales from Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*): Study of past metal contamination from a copper mine (Ulla River, NW Iberian Peninsula). Online. *Chemosphere*. 2017, roč. 188, č. neuvedeno, s. 18-24. ISSN 00456535. Dostupné z: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.08.094>. [cit. 2025-02-11].
- DAŇKOVÁ, Monika. *Prvky podskupiny mědi*. Online. Masarykova univerzita v Brně, 2016. Dostupné z: https://is.muni.cz/el/pep/podzim2016/CH2BP_3P1P/um/SkupinaMediDankovaMonika.pdf. [cit. 2025-02-10].
- DOBROTOVÁ, Zuzana. *Stanovení obsahu rtuti v rybách řeky Dřevnice a jejích přítoků*. Online, Diplomová práce, vedoucí doc. RNDr. Lubomír Šimek CSc. Zlín: Univerzita Tomáše Bati ve Zlíně, Fakulta technologická, Ústav chemie., 2011. Dostupné z: <https://digilib.k.utb.cz/handle/10563/17194>. [cit. 2025-02-09].
- DVOŘÁK, Petr; PYSZKO, Martin; VELÍŠEK, Josef; DVOŘÁKOVÁ-LÍŠKOVÁ, Zuzana a ANDREJI, Jaroslav. *Anatomie a fyziologie ryb*. 2. aktualizované vydání. Vodňany: Jihočeská univerzita v Českých Budějovicích, Fakulta rybářství a ochrany vod, 2020. ISBN 978-80-7514-109-5.
- GAMAKARANAGE, Champika SSK; RODRIGO, Chaturaka; WEERASINGHE, Sajitha; GNANATHASAN, Ariarane; PUVANARAJ, Visvalingam et al. Complications and management of acute copper sulphate poisoning; a case discussion. Online. *Journal of Occupational Medicine and Toxicology*. 2011, roč. 6, č. 1, s. 1-4. ISSN 1745-6673. Dostupné z: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1745-6673-6-34>. [cit. 2025-02-11].
- HORÁČEK, Miroslav. *Atlas ryb - základy ichtologie*. Online. Chytej.cz. 2010. Dostupné z: <https://www.chytej.cz/atlas-ryb/zaklady-ichtologie/>. [cit. 2025-02-09].
- HORÁČEK, Miroslav. *Atlas ryb - jelec tloušť*. Online. MRK.cz. 2017. Dostupné z: https://www.mrk.cz/r/atlas/atlas_ryb/maloostni/kaproviti/jelec_tloust/. [cit. 2025-02-09].
- HORÁČEK, Miroslav. *Atlas ryb - jelec tloušť*. Online. Chytej.cz. 2010. Dostupné z: <https://www.chytej.cz/atlas-ryb/jelec-tloust/>. [cit. 2025-02-09].
- JANÁKOVÁ, Lucie. *Kruhoustí*. Online. Olomouc: Slovanské gymnázium Olomouc, 2013. Dostupné z: <https://docs.sgo.cz/uploads/category/49/doc/kruhousti.pdf>. [cit. 2025-02-08].
- JONÁKOVÁ, Šárka. *Paryby a Ryby*. Online. Příbram: Waldorfská škola Příbram, 2012. Dostupné z: https://www.waldorf.pb.cz/dum/dumy/VY_32_INOVACE_I-3/VY_32_INOVACE_PRSJ_I-3_13.pdf. [cit. 2025-02-15].
- JOVIČIĆ, Katarina; JANKOVIĆ, Saša; NIKOLIĆ, Dragica M.; ĐIKANOVIĆ, Vesna; SKORIĆ, Stefan et al. Prospects of fish scale and fin samples usage for nonlethal monitoring of metal contamination: a study on five fish species from the Danube River. Online. *Knowledge & Management of Aquatic Ecosystems*. 2023, roč. 154, č. 4, s. 1-7. ISSN 1961-9502. Dostupné z: <https://doi.org/10.1051/kmae/2022027>. [cit. 2025-02-11].
- KANICKÝ, Viktor; KUČERA, Jan; TOMÁŠEK, Vladimír a HELÁN, Václav. *Analýza anorganických látek*. Český Těšín: 2 Theta, 2021-2023. ISBN 978-80-88279-06-8. [cit. 2025-02-11].
- KANICKÝ, Viktor. *Hmotnostní spektrometrie s indukčně vázaným plazmatem ICP-MS: učební text*. Neuvedeno. 2007. Dostupné z: https://is.muni.cz/el/sci/jaro2007/C6300/Kanicky_ICP_MS_vyuka.pdf. [cit. 2025-02-11].
- KHAN, Muhammad Ismail. *Fish Anatomy and Functionality*. Online. Breeze Fish Point, 2024. Dostupné z: <https://breezefishpoint.com/explore-the-body-parts-of-a-fish/>. [cit. 2025-04-12].
- MENDELOVA UNIVERZITA V BRNĚ. *Kůže, šupiny a zbarvení ryb*. Online. Brno: Oddělení rybářství a hydrobiologie, 2000, s. 1–5. Dostupné z: <http://www.rybarstvi.eu/dok%20rybari/ichtologie/KUZE.pdf>. [cit. 2025-02-09].
- MUSILOVÁ, Zuzana. *Nová fylogeneze paprskoploutvých ryb*. Živa. Online. 2016, roč. 2016, č. 4. Praha: Academia, SŠ AV ČR. ISSN 0044-4812. Dostupné z: <https://ziva.avcr.cz/files/ziva/pd/pdf/nova-fylogeneze-paprskoploutvych-ryb.pdf>. [cit. 2025-02-15].
- NOVÁKOVÁ, Hana. *Stanovení těžkých kovů v rybích šupinách metodou ICP - MS*. Online, Bakalářská práce, vedoucí Mgr. Markéta Holá, Ph.D. Brno: Masarykova univerzita, Přírodovědecká fakulta, Ústav chemie., 2009. Dostupné z: https://is.muni.cz/th/u2pzd/Bakalarska_prace.pdf. [cit. 2025-02-13].
- Prispěvatel WikiSkript. *Měď*. Online. WikiSkripta. ©2022. Dostupné z: <https://www.wikiskripta.eu/w/M%C4%9B%C4%8F>. [cit. 2025-02-10].

Prispěvatelé WikiSkript. *Kontaminace kovy*. Online. WikiSkripta. ©2023. Dostupné z: https://www.wikiskripta.eu/w/Kontaminace_kovy. [cit. 2025-02-10].

STAROVE, Tomáš. *Ryby – anatomie*. Online. SlidePlayer.cz, 2013. Dostupné z: <https://slideplayer.cz/slide/12082757/>. [cit. 2025-02-08].

SULTANA, Tayyaba; SIDDIQUE, Amir; SULTANA, Salma; MAHBOOB, Shahid; AL-GHANIM, Khalid et al. Fish scales as a non-lethal tool of the toxicity of wastewater from the River Chenab. Online. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2017, roč. 24, č. 3, s. 2464-2475. ISSN 0944-1344. Dostupné z: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-016-7962-9>. [cit. 2025-02-11].

ŠÍMA, Petr. *Biologie: pro 2. ročník gymnázií*. 2023. Praha: Eduko, 2023. ISBN 978-80-88473-17-6.

ŠÍPEK, Antonín. *Úvod do populační teratologie*. Online. Praha, 2011. Dostupné z: http://www.vrozenevady.cz/prezentace/pdf/UDPT_ILFUK_2011.pdf [cit. 2025-02-16].

VELÍŠEK, Josef. *Vodní toxikologie pro rybáře*. Vodňany: Jihočeská univerzita v Českých Budějovicích, Fakulta rybářství a ochrany vod, 2014. ISBN 978-80-87437-89-6. Dostupné také z: <http://krameriusndk.nkp.cz/search/handle/uuid:11578040-01e0-11e9-bc37-005056827e51>.